

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH

Allambergenova Maftuna Maksudovna

Student of Karakalpak state university

Abstract: This article provides information about educational technologies of speech development in communicative culture. At the same time, the important features of developing students' speech are described.

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The method of speech development is inextricably linked with other special methods of preschool education, because speech is one of the most important means of full development of a child's personality. Understanding the speech of others and the active speech of the child is necessary in any pedagogical process. Speech accompanies the child in all his activities. Intellect, that is, the ability to understand the external world with the help of memory, imagination, imagination, thinking, as well as speech - these are important characteristics that distinguish a person from an animal. And both intelligence and speech appear in a person in early childhood, and in a teenager and a young man, they rapidly improve, not only because his organism is developing, but also when this person also acquires speech.

Educational technologies make significant changes in the development of students' dialogic speech. Educational technologies make the learning process more convenient and help students learn. This plays an important role in the development of students' dialogic speech. Educational technologies can develop students' dialogic speech in the following ways:

1. Increasing students' self-expression: Educational technologies increase students' self-expression. This helps to develop students' dialogic speech. It allows students to express themselves, learn and share their ideas with others.

2. Interactive learning modules: Educational technologies help make learning modules interactive. Interactive learning modules help students understand the content. This will be important in the development of students' dialogic speech.

3. Online Webinars: Online webinars are important in improving student interaction and discussion. This helps to develop students' dialogic speech. Online webinars help students express themselves and increase interaction with others.

4. Tests and questions: Educational technologies help to create tests and questions. Quizzes and quizzes are important in checking students' understanding and mastery of course content.

5. Video lessons: Video lessons help students to improve their understanding of the content. This will be important in the development of students' dialogic speech.

The role of educational technologies in increasing students' expression of their opinions is also important in the development of their scientific and creative activities. Students will have the opportunity to exchange their ideas with others through the virtual environment created by educational technologies, forums, blogs, electronic libraries and other means of communication.

These allow students to exchange ideas and generate new ideas about their perspectives, interests, and growing experiences during their student years. As a result, students have the opportunity to develop their ideas with their teachers, friends and other students, and this is very important in developing their dialogic speech and learning new knowledge.

Also, educational technology offers the best way for students to express themselves. Virtual environments and the ease of student participation provide ample opportunities for students to express themselves. This will help them to develop and improve their interest in interacting with their teachers and other students.

It is known that the teaching of a number of subjects includes targeted teaching, increasing student motivation, self-assessment and mastery, problem solving and many other processes. This makes it easier for students to develop dialogic speech and to express their opinions.

In particular, the great role of educational technologies in the development of students' dialogic speech and increasing the expression of their opinion. Yes, it is very important. Interactive learning modules allow students to review, test, and master the learning material. Interactivity requires the use of a scientific-educational method that makes the learning modules interesting, engaging and developmental for the student.

Interactive learning modules allow students to learn at their own time and in their own way. At the same time, the modules ensure students' mastery of information and independent learning. Such modules also increase students' self-expression, as they allow them to master the coordination, analysis and explanation of their own thinking. These are important for the development of students' dialogic speech. Indeed, online webinars are one of the best tools of educational technology in developing student interaction. Online webinars are forms of e-sports that students can participate in from their home, generation, and region. Online webinars allow students to upload, explain, and discuss information. At the same time, online webinars allow students to master their experiences, that is, to increase the exchange and negotiation between students.

Online webinars are very important for the development of students' dialogic speech, because they force students to negotiate and allow them to express their opinions, answer questions and influence others. These help students to self-explain and engage in coherent negotiation, which develops students' communication skills and at the same time allows students to communicate their ideas to others for cognitive change and mastery. It also develops reading skills.

Educational technologies help create tests and questions, check that students fully understand the content, and ensure their mastery. Tests and questions help to assess, process or analyze the level of knowledge of students.